

MEMBRANES OF PDLLA/BIOGLASS[®] WITH ASYMMETRIC BIOACTIVITY FOR BIOMEDICAL APPLICATIONS.

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SUMMARY

The aim of this study is to investigate the production of biocompatible and biodegradable membranes with an asymmetric bioactivity, which contains inorganic particles with an osteoconductive gradient concentration along the material thickness. In this work the proof-of-concept is made using poly (DL-lactic acid) membranes exhibiting the presence of Bioglass[®] particles in just one of the sides. The results show that such composite films could find applications in guided bone regeneration.

Keywords: Asymmetric membrane; Gradient of concentration; Bioactive glass; Polylactide.

INTRODUCTION

In the last years, composites of polymers, natural and synthetic, and bioactive inorganic materials have been developed as bone-repairing devices due to their bioactivity, biocompatibility and biodegradability properties [1]. Therefore, the properties of these composite materials can be tailored, and advantages can be taken just by conjugating the properties of each of its component (polymer and bioactive inorganic material). For example, bioactivity or porosity can be induced in a polymer adding a glass ceramic. This kind of composite materials can be very useful in guided tissue regeneration (GTR) for the regeneration of periodontal tissues, bone around natural teeth and dental implants[2]. Guided tissue regeneration is a well known technique that repairs tissue defect or reconstructs new tissue by using a barrier membrane to protect the defect site from invasion of other tissue (as fibrous connective tissue) [3]. Advantages can be taken by using this kind of composite materials. For example, one side of the membrane can be impermeable or less porous preventing the ingrowth of fibrous connective tissue into the defect area and the other side can be more porous allowing cells to colonize it to

promote bone regeneration, or bioactive allowing the mineralisation of the damage tissue[4, 5]. In this context, the purpose of this study was to prepare biodegradable composite membranes with asymmetric bioactivity and adequate mechanical properties.

Membranes of poly (DL-lactic acid) (PDLLA) with Bioglass® (BG) were prepared by an adapted solvent casting method. The surface morphology of the membrane was characterized using Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) and Contact Angle (CA). The bioactivity degree of the sample was measured by studying the formation of hydroxyapatite (HA) on the surface by immersion in simulated body fluid (SBF) during 2, 7, 14 and 21 days[6]. The ability for calcium phosphate deposition was analyzed in both faces of the membranes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

Poly-DL-lactic (PDLLA) with an inherent viscosity of 1.87 dL/g was purchased from Purasorb and was used as received. A bioactive glass (BG) (45S5 Bioglass) with the following composition: 45 SiO₂, 24.5 CaO, 24.5 Na₂O and 6.0 P₂O₅ in wt%, was supplied by US Biomaterials Corp. (Florida, USA). The particle size of BG, measured by laser scattering analysis (Coulter LS 100 particle size analyzer), was found to be lower than 20 µm. All other reagents and solvents used were of reagent grade and were used without further purification.

Membranes preparation

All the membranes were prepared based on a solvent casting technique. The PDLLA films were prepared by dissolving 0.50g of PDLLA in 30ml of chloroform. After total dissolution, the solution was transferred to a Petri dish with 9cm of diameter. The Petri dish had to be aligned into a horizontal position to facilitate the formation of a cast film with uniform thickness. The assembly was kept in a chemical hood for 24h (cover the assembly with an aluminium sheet), and CHCl₃ was allowed to evaporate at a very slow rate. Then, the films were vacuum dried for 48h at 40°C.

The PDLLA/BG membranes were prepared in the exact same process as the membranes above with the difference in the composition of the membrane. The PDLLA/BG membranes were prepared by dissolving 0.40g of PDLLA in 30ml of chloroform. After total dissolution, 0.10g of Bioglass® was dispersed in the above solution, creating an 80/20 of PDLLA/BG membrane.

Bioactivity tests

For the *in vitro* bioactivity tests an acellular simulated body fluid (SBF) (1.0x) was prepared, with ions concentration nearly equal to human blood plasma. The SBF composition and preparation was previously describes by Kokubo and co-workers[6]. Sample membranes of 200*150mm² were cut from the original processed films for the bioactivity tests. Three replicates for each sample were immersed in SBF for 2, 5, 7, 14 and 21 days at 37° C. After being removed from SBF the sample membranes were gently rinsed with distilled water and dried at room temperature.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

The morphological analysis of the samples (after and before of bioactivity test) was performed using Scanning Electron Microscope (Nova NanoSEM 200-FEI Company).at an accelerated voltage of 15 kV. Before being observed by SEM, the membranes had to be gold coated using a Hitachi coating unit IB-2 coater at 6 mA.

Energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS)

PDLLA and composite membranes prepared were observed by a Field Emission Gun/Scanning Electron Microscopy (FEG/SEM) - Nova NanoSEM 200 (FEI Company) with an integrated system EDS/EBDS - EDAX - Pegasus X4M (EDS - energy dispersive spectrometer /EBSD - Electron Backscatter Diffraction) to obtain simultaneous collection of EDS (chemistry) and EBSD (crystallography) data. The samples were fixed by mutual conductive adhesive tape on aluminium stubs and covered with carbon palladium using a sputter coater. Before and after immersion in SBF the samples were analysed in order to check the appearance of a calcium-phosphate layer on the surface of the matrixes.

X-ray diffraction (XRD)

X-ray diffraction analysis on samples before and after immersion in SBF was performed to characterise the crystalline/amorphous nature of the films and to identify any crystalline phases present after immersion in SBF (results were compared to non immersed controls). The membranes were analysed recording the wide-angle X-ray scattering (WAXS) patterns in a Philips PW1710 reflection diffractometer (Almelo, The Netherlands), with a step ($2\theta=0.02^\circ$) scanning time of 2s and Cu-K α -radiation generated at 40 kV and 30 mA.

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy with KBr (FTIR)

Membranes were analysed by infrared spectroscopy to assess the chemical structure of the polymeric microparticles before and after soaking in SBF. Spectra were recorded in an IRPrestige 21 FTIR spectrophotometer with the attenuated total reflection accessory (128 scans, resolution 4 cm⁻¹) in the spectral range 2000-400cm⁻¹.

Water Contact Angle Measurements (CA)

The hydrophilicity of the samples was assessed by evaluating the surface wettability by water contact angle measurements. Static contact angle measurements were carried out by the sessile drop method using a contact angle meter (model OCA 15+) with a high-performance image processing system from DataPhysics Instruments (Filderstadt, Germany). A drop (3 μ L) of water was added by a motor driven syringe at room temperature. Two different samples of each material were used and at least three measurements were carried out for each sample.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The bioactive character of the composite membranes produced was tested *in vitro* by analyzing the apatite formation at the material surface after exposure to SBF. Any calcification occurred in the two surfaces of the membranes was investigated using SEM (see figure 1). No apatite was formed in the un-filled PDLLA and in the upper face of the composite membrane even after 21 days of immersion in SBF. Only the down face of the composite membrane presents a bioactive character as an uniform ceramic layer could be detected even after 2 days of immersion of SBF. This layer is compatible with an apatite-like layer exhibiting a cauliflower morphology resulting from the assembly of nano-size needle calcium phosphate crystals.

Figure1. SEM images of the PDLLA and PDLLA/BG membranes after immersion in SBF for different periods. Two magnifications are shown for each case.

The morphological analysis was complemented with energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) performed in the calcified side of the composite membrane after incubation in SBF for 2 days (see figure 2). The result indicates that indeed the ionic composition of the layer consists mainly on Ca and P. Although no quantitative data can be taken from the EDS spectra obtained we can conclude from the relative intensity of the Ca and P peaks that a thicker layer of apatite is formed in the composite membranes. More insights of the nature of the CaP coating formed could be obtained from X-ray diffraction and FTIR.

Figure2. EDS of the composite membrane at the under face after 2 days in SBF.

The XRD patterns of the PDLLA/BG membranes after 21 days incubation in SBF are shown in Fig.3a. After incubation in SBF, the membrane showed the main characteristic peak of hydroxyapatite at $2\theta = 32^\circ$ (contribution of the (211), (112) and (300) planes of apatite) and the others at $2\theta = 22.9^\circ$ ((111) diffraction peak) which is characteristic of the Ca-P layer formed.

The FTIR spectrum of the PDLLA/BG membrane after incubation in SBF (after 14 days) showed the presence of phosphate (PO_4^{3-}) and carbonate (CO_3^{2-}) groups (Figure 3b). This means that the apatite formed on the surface of membrane was incorporated with carbonate ion, similar to the bone apatite. In the spectra, the transmittance band around 1010 cm^{-1} , correspond to the stretching and bending vibrations of PO_4^{3-} and other one at around 606 cm^{-1} . The absorption peaks of the CO_3^{2-} were also detected at 878 cm^{-1} and at around 1500 cm^{-1} .

Figure3. a) XRD patterns of PDLLA/BG membranes after 21 days in SBF and b) FTIR spectra of the PDLLA/BG membrane after 14 days in SBF.

We can conclude with the SEM, EDS, XRD and FTIR results that the composite membranes could induce the precipitation of a bone-like apatite layer in just one of the sides of the membrane. Such data suggests that the concentration of BG particles along the membranes' thickness should not be homogeneous. Figure 4 shows the cross-section observation of a composite membrane where it is clear that the BG particles are concentrated just in the under side of the membrane. Besides influencing the bioactivity character of each side of the membranes, the asymmetric distribution of BG particles could also influence other properties, such as the wettability.

Figure4. SEM picture of the developed composite membrane along its thickness. The BG particles could be detected just in the under side of the membrane being the upper side composed just of PDLLA.

To examine the hydrophilicity of the membranes, their water contact angles were measured, and the results are provided in Table 1. It can be seen that both PDLLA and PDLLA/BG upper face have an advancing contact angle $>75^\circ$ indicating their moderate hydrophobic character. The presence of BG in the under face distinctly decreases the contact angle of the composite membrane (60.7°) becoming more hydrophilic.

Table1. Water Contact Angle (θ_a) of PDLLA and PDLLA/BG membranes

Sample	Face	θ_a ($^\circ$)
PDLLA		75.7 ± 2.1
PDLLA/BG	upper	80.0 ± 1.1
	under	60.7 ± 1.4

CONCLUSIONS

Asymmetric membranes could be easily obtained by a solvent casting technique. It was reported that the composite membranes have a bioactive behaviour that is confirmed by all the techniques employed. Moreover, the bioactive character of the composite membrane its only verify in the under face of PDLLA/BG membrane. The results of this investigation confirm that the method of production used in this composite system allows the obtainment of membranes that exhibit one face with osteoconductive properties that being important for guided bone regeneration and regenerative medicine applications.

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